

How to make a future health workforce happen? Policy, practice and people

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Book of abstracts

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Here is to you, with deep thanks!
To those who are tireless fighting the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic at the frontlines of healthcare systems in Europe and across the globe, putting their own health and safety at risk, and to the many healthcare workers who have lost their lives during the pandemic.

Organisation

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Health workforce and primary task: practice and people

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Due to the significance of health sectors, a persistent analysis of new ways of improving work in health sector is very important. Today health systems represent a special challenge for studying group processes and dynamics inside them. An innovative approach of systems-psychodynamic organizational consulting could improve leadership in health institutions. Health organizations (the primary, secondary or tertiary level) have some common organizational characteristics, determined by the Law on Health Care and other regulations, but also a lot of diversity in organizational culture. The boundaries of organizations in health are less rigid than before, and less tight. Professional and other networks of influence are more developed; the openness and flow of information are more present, as well as partnership and cooperation, but also mobility, mechanisms of disintegration, which are all the more visible in the health sector. Health organizations follow the changes which happen in all other sectors. It is necessary, therefore, to develop the awareness of risks and knowledge about managing the risks of modern organizations of managers, employees and members of the health care organization, in order to overcome disintegration and crisis of trust to the best possible measure. Instability is present in health organizations as in all others, so it is necessary to look for the ways of sustainable functioning. Health organizations are subject to the influence of numerous outer factors, as well as all other organizations and individuals. Relations in health organizations are consequences of external factors, but also of internal norms rooted in them. Having in mind the state of the health sector, this paper represent possibility of using the psycho-dynamic organizational approach in work with organizations of health sector. Psycho-dynamic organizational approach in work with healthcare workforce influences the development of work results in the health system.

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Psychodynamic organizational approach in work with healthcare workforce influences the development of work results in the health system.